

Figure S2. Alternate OxCal posterior age model excluding OSL sample USU-2902. For details of OSL and radiocarbon dates refer to Tables 1 and 2, respectively, in the main body of the manuscript text. R_Combine RC12 is combination of the two dates presented in Table 2.

OxCal v4.3.2 Bronk Ramsey (2017); r:5 SHCal13 atmospheric curve (Hogg et al 2013)

